

The Impact of Utilizing Gagne's Instructional Strategy for Teaching A-Scan Biometry to Undergraduate Medical Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Gagne, Tuckman's Group Development Model, Small Group Discussion</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5750000</p>	<p>Introduction</p> <p><i>A structured approach is important when teaching procedural and clinical skills to medical students; otherwise, most learners would feel incompetent when performing the skill independently. This study aimed to investigate the impact of using Gagne's instructional plan in teaching A-scan biometry to undergraduate medical students.</i></p> <p>Methods:</p> <p><i>A total of 96 4th year medical students of the Islamabad Medical and Dental College rotating in the ophthalmology clerkship were recruited in the study. The students were randomly distributed into 8 groups of 12 each, each one of these groups was then randomly allocated to either one of the two learning strategies i.e., small group discussion or Gagne's instructional model. The students were assessed via direct observation of their performance by a trained preceptor. Test of significance, and correlation analysis was carried between the scores of the two instructional strategies using SPSS version 20.0. A p-value of < 0.05 was deemed significant.</i></p> <p><i>Results: The mean score for students instructed via Gagne's instructional model was 6.60 (± 0.94) while that of the groups instructed via small group discussion was 5.87 (± 1.26). The mean score obtained by students instructed via Gagne's instructional model was significantly higher than that obtained by students instructed via small group discussion. ($P = 0.002$).</i></p> <p><i>Conclusion: This study shows the positive effects of using Gagne's instructional model on medical students learning to perform A-scan biometry. It is recommended that future studies be done to assess the effects of this instructional strategy in medical education.</i></p>

Introduction

Robert Gagne was an American psychologist who, by conducting a series of studies that simplified what he believed was 'good instruction'. He worked with air force pilots during World War II and devised an instructional strategy that enabled the pilots to master flying in the most efficient manner (McDonald & West, 2020). The teaching of medical skills is analogous to military instruction: both have behaviorist roots and concentrate on bringing about the desired change in behavior (learning the requisite skill) in the most competent manner possible.

Gagne's instructional principles are based on what he refers to as the 'conditions of learning' which have been further qualified by him as being either internal or external. Internal conditions deal with the learner's previously acquired competencies while external conditions are the stimuli that are offered to him from outside. Implementation of his instructional model begins with the identification of the learning objectives. The preceptor then determines the conditions that are necessary for achieving these objectives. Subsequently, the instructional events required to support the learning process are determined and incorporated into the lesson plan. In essence, these events serve as the foundation for the lesson plan and are postulated to facilitate the transfer of knowledge from perception to memory.

A structured approach is especially important when teaching procedural and clinical skills, if these sessions lack structure and design most learners would feel incompetent when attempting the task independently (Shah & Chincholi, 2018).

Since the introduction of competency based medical curricula, traditional didactic lectures have been gradually replaced by learning strategies which are more student centric (Raut, Shreechakradhar, More, Rathod, Gujar, Rajhans & Kale, 2014). Small group discussion is one of these strategies; it is based on the 'development model' formulated by Bruce Tuckman (Meo, 2013). Although often described as comprising of between 8-12 members, a small group is not really defined by its size; it is the way in which the teacher facilitates the learning process that establishes it. For the learning session to be meaningful, the facilitator must be aware of group dynamics;

the framework provided by Tuckman enables educators to make their sessions more purposeful (McKimm & Morris, 2009). Typically described as including the following stages: forming, storming, norming and performing Tuckman's model allows a small group to function as a unit enabling all the members to achieve the set objectives effectively. It thus forms a useful learning and teaching strategy especially in the context of clinical teaching.

A-Scan biometry is a diagnostic technique used to determine the power of an intra-ocular lens that is implanted in the eye at the time of cataract surgery. One of the methods involves an ultrasonic probe placed on the cornea and a beam of (ultrasonic) waves projected into the eye to determine the length of the eye ball. The corneal curvatures are determined via the process of keratometry and the information obtained is fed into a formula to calculate the power of the lens that is to be implanted. Keeping in mind the complex nature of the skill (A-scan biometry) that we desire learners to acquire in the shortest time possible, a lesson plan based on Gagne's instructional model (which includes nine steps) may help align the learning activity with its objectives, ensure that the different learning styles of the members of the audience are catered to and make certain that the mode of assessment used to determine if the requisite competency has been acquired by the learner is appropriate (Okey, 1991).

Since cataract is a very common cause of decreased vision in the elderly (Singh, Pardhan & Kulothungan, Swaminathan, Ravichandaran, Ganesan, Sharma, & Raman, 2019) It is one of the requisite outcomes of the Ophthalmology clerkship at our institute that the graduating medical student be able to recognize it and be able to formulate a management plan for a patient presenting with this disorder. This management plan often includes the performance of A-scan biometry to determine the power of the intra ocular lens that must be implanted in the eye at the end of cataract surgery to restore its power. The feedback given to the clerkship team by students often indicates that they (students) struggle with the key concepts regarding A-Scan biometry despite the fact that they are given hands on training during the clerkship.

The purpose of this study was to determine the impact of using Gagne's instructional plan while teaching A-scan biometry to undergraduate medical student and compare it to small group discussion which is the learning strategy currently in use.

Materials and methods.

Study setting and design.

This cross-sectional study was conducted between January and September 2020 over a period of nine months at the Department of Ophthalmology of the Islamabad Medical and Dental College, Islamabad, Pakistan.

Sample size, inclusion, and exclusion criteria

After obtaining approval from the Institutional Review Board (IRB), 96 fourth year medical students of the Islamabad Medical and Dental College (class of 2021) rotating in the Ophthalmology clerkship were recruited in the study. Students who were repeating the clerkship as well as those doing an elective rotation were excluded. A full disclosure of the study objectives and methods were made and informed consent was obtained from all the participants.

Sampling technique and data collection

The students were randomly distributed, using a lottery system, into 8 batches of 12 each. Each one of these batches was then, using a computer, randomly allocated to either one of the two groups based on the type of learning strategy used i.e., small group discussion (Group I) or Gagne's instructional model (Group II). The learning sessions were conducted by a single preceptor with at least 7 years of teaching experience in Ophthalmology. The participants were informed that they would be assessed at the end of the session using a checklist encompassing the competencies they were required to master. This checklist was provided to them at the beginning of the session.

The lesson plans based on Gagne's instructional strategy and Tuckman's framework are shown in table 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Lesson plan based on Tuckman's framework

Time	Preceptor led Activity	Student Activity
10 30 am (Forming)	The preceptor will introduce herself and the topic. Lay down ground rules. Outline the objectives.	Get seated. Introduce themselves.
10 40-11 00 am (Storming)	Present tasks. Ensure the group understands the tasks. Provide learning guidance as required.	Divide tasks Go over and if required add to the learning objectives. Make sure they are comfortable and are able to see/hear/write without unnecessary strain.
11 00-11 20 am (Norming)	Ensure that the group is on track. Ensure objectives are being met. Provide learning guidance	Come up with a mutually agreeable plan. Learn to work as a group. Present learning objectives to the preceptor
11 20-11 55 am (Performing)	Rate student performance on standardized checklist. Provide feedback	Perform A-scan biometry on a simulated patient. Discuss results with preceptor.
11 55-12 00 pm (Adjourning)	Help group members wind up once task is successfully completed	Break up.

Table 2: Lesson plan based on Gagne's instructional strategy

Time	Content and preceptor led learning activity	Student activity
	Consent & Sanitizes instills Centers Interprets Calculates TOTAL explanation of hands and anesthetic agent probe on Scan IOL Power procedure (0.5) equipment aseptically eye (2) (3.5) (8) (1) (0.5) (0.5)	
10:30 am	Introduction of preceptor and the topic. Grabbing of audience attention by experimenting with a container with rubber bands tied around it to demonstrate the properties of sound waves.	Get seated. Introduce themselves. Experiment with ice-cream cups with rubber bands around them to answer questions about the properties of sound and how it differs from ultrasound.
10:40 am	Point out objectives. Give a brief outline of the program. Make sure everyone has a copy of the handout.	Go over and add to the learning objectives. Make sure they are comfortable and are able to see/hear/write without unnecessary strain.
10:45 am	Recall of prior knowledge. Review the anatomy of the eye via the use of a model. Discuss properties of ultrasonic waves via an interactive group discussion and an animation.	Identify the requisite ocular structures. Recall properties of ultrasonic waves and list them on the white board. Watch an animation to further clear concepts and enhance understanding
10:55am	Presentation of the content , using PowerPoint. Content must be in palatable portions that are about 10 minutes each.	Add to the handouts. Presentation technique will be largely interactive with the participants answering the questions posed by the preceptor.
11:15am	Provide learning guidance via demonstration of the technique of A scan biometry on a simulated patient by the preceptor.	Observe the preceptor while she performs the scan. Will be asked to perform tasks that allow application of knowledge.
11:25am	Five-minute break to recuperate.	
11:30am	Elicit performance: Observe participants directly while they perform the skill.	Break up in pairs. Perform the ophthalmic ultrasound on a simulated patient under the guidance of their facilitator
11:45	Provide feedback on the participants' performance (formative assessment) Grade performance on pre designed assessment proforma. (Summative assessment)	Ask questions to clarify concepts. Construct new knowledge on the scaffolding provided by the preceptor
11:55am	Enhance retention of the acquired skill via provision of sample ophthalmic A-scans that the participants can study. Provide links to on line learning resources. Invite questions. Answer to the participants' satisfaction.	Pose and answer questions Discuss with peers/preceptors
12:00pm	Conclude and break up the session.	Collect their learning material and leave the venue.

At the conclusion of the learning session, the students were assessed via direct observation of their performance by another trained preceptor who was blind to the instructional strategy utilized and had at least 7 years of teaching experience in Ophthalmology. A checklist was used to record the scores of the students. This is shown in table 3.

Table 3: Student assessment checklist.

(Numbers in parenthesis indicate marks for each of the assessed categories.)

Statistical analysis

The student identification numbers along with their scores and the learning strategy utilized were entered into the database. Descriptive statistics (mean with standard deviation) were used to describe student scores. Independent sample t-test was employed to determine the significance of the results (score of students in the two groups) using IBM Statistical Package for Social Sciences version 20.0. A p-value of < 0.05 was taken as significant.

Results and Discussion

A total of 96 fourth year medical students were enrolled in the study of which 36 (37.5%) were males and 60 (62.5%) were females. Half of these students ($n=46$, 19 males and 27 females) were instructed via Gagne's instructional plan (Group I) while the remaining half ($n=46$, 15 males and 31 females) were instructed via small group discussion (Group II). The mean score of the students instructed via Gagne's lesson plan was $6.60 (\pm 0.94)$ while that of the groups instructed via small group discussion was $5.87 (\pm 1.26)$. The mean score obtained by students instructed via Gagne's instructional model was significantly higher than that obtained by students instructed via small group discussion. ($p= 0.002$).

The Objective of this study was to compare the educational impact of Gagne's instructional plan to small group discussion (based on Tuckman's framework) in teaching A-scan biometry to undergraduate medical students. Gagne's instructional plan has been utilized by medical teachers for imparting important procedural skills as well as revamping lectures delivered to both under and post graduate medical students (Ademola-Poopla, Nzeh, Saka, Olokoba&Obajolowo, 2016). To the knowledge of the authors' this is the only study to date that compares this instructional strategy to small group discussion; another widely employed strategy. A comparison of these techniques may allow clinical teachers to choose the most efficient approach to impart important procedural skills to students in a limited amount of time.

Our investigation comparing the two strategies shows that the mean scores of the students instructed via a lesson plan based on Gagne's nine steps were significantly higher than those of students who were taught through small group discussions (6.60 ± 0.94 vs 5.87 ± 1.26 $p=0.002$). These results are corroborated by the conclusions drawn by several researchers who employed this structured approach while teaching procedural skills to undergraduate medical students as well as health care professionals. Ng's modification of this framework in the light of Peyton's four steps yielded similar results: the author reported that a majority of the students who were instructed via this method felt more confident in performing slit lamp examination after attending the interactive session. (Ng, 2014). The feedback provided by the students attending these sessions was positive with all the students agreeing that they felt more confident while performing slit lamp eye examination after attending this session. 50% of these students concluded that they strongly agreed with this sentiment. Wong, (2018) employed Gagne's instructional strategy while teaching health care professionals including optometrists and ophthalmic nurses how to measure the intra ocular pressure via Goldman Applanation tonometry (GAT). The author deduced that this approach was superior to the current practice of GAT training which includes some form of exposure to the skill, going over pre-course reading material, attending a tutorial and then finally performing the skill. In contrast, not only does a lesson plan based on Gagne's strategy allow participants from various levels of training to be involved, it also makes prior exposure unnecessary.

In addition to Ophthalmologists, these findings were also validated by researchers from other fields of medicine who concluded that the infrastructure provided by Gagne made learning more holistic and effective especially in the delivery of a diverse set of psychomotor skills. This is in line with the results of our study. Khadooji, Rostami & Ishaq, (2011) concluded that, in addition to catering to different learning styles, Gagne's instructional plan also provides a structured approach that is applicable when a diverse set of practical skills such as the insertion of a peritoneal drain are taught to under and postgraduate medical professionals.

Gagne's instructional plan was also found to be associated with improved performance of the facilitators' involved in the learning session (Ullah, Rehman & Bibi, 2015). The authors of this two-phase study delivered a series of four traditional didactic lectures in the first phase. Phase 2 of this study included learning sessions based on Gagne's instructional plan. The authors concluded that the adoption of a structured approach to learning enhanced both comprehension and retention of knowledge both findings that were similar to the results obtained by us. The number of students ($n=15$) in each session of this study was also similar to ours ($n=12$). In contrast to our study, however, an objective comparison Gagne's plan to another learning strategy (small group discussion) was not sought. Also, in contrast to our study, the participants were post-graduate residents and radiographers; our study population included only 4th year medical students.

Large group interactive lectures based on Gagne's plan have also been compared to a traditional didactic lecture (Ali & Ali, 2015). The authors of this study concluded that there was a significant improvement in student

scores ($n=100$, $p<0.001$) when instructed via Gagne's plan. This is similar to the findings of our study ($n=96$ $p=0.002$). In contrast to our study however, the number of students in each learning session was large ($n=100$ vs $n=12$) and a practical skill was not imparted.

The limitations of our study include that a single cohort of students was under investigation and that we only sought to teach a procedural skill. However, Gagne's 9 steps have behaviorist roots and were initially developed with the aim of teaching skills in the most efficient manner.

Conclusion

A lesson plan based on Gagne's 9 steps is better than one carried out in traditional small groups based on the framework provided by Tuckman. This is especially important if a session that seeks to impart a practical or procedural skill.

Recommendations

Gagne's instructional framework should be adopted by and used by medical teachers especially in situations where procedural skills are taught. Faculty development workshops that enhance familiarity with this strategy should be conducted in medical institutes across the country.

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